

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

It gives me great pleasure to announce the fourth regular issue of 2024. I would like to thank all the authors for their sound research papers and the editorial board and our guest reviewers for their extremely valuable reviews and suggestions for improvement. These contributions and the generous support of the consortium members enable us to run our journal and maintain its quality. I would also like to thank our broader community for reading and incorporating sound J.UCS papers into their research. I am also very proud to announce that our journal has been included in the Free Journal Network as one of the listed high-quality journals in this field.

Still, I would like to expand our editorial board: If you are a tenured associate professor or above with a good publication record, please apply to join our editorial board. We are also interested in receiving high-quality proposals for special issues on new topics and emerging trends.

In this regular issue, I am very pleased to introduce six papers by 22 authors from nine countries: Brazil, Czech Republic, Germany, Iran, Jordan, Portugal, Thailand, Turkey, and the USA.

In a collaboration between researchers from the Czech Republic and Germany, Sivaramasamy Elayaraja, Sunil Yeruva Vlastimil Stejskal, and Satish Nandipati look into multi-class microscopic image analysis of protozoan parasites using convolutional neural network and perform a study on 4740 microscopic images.

André Diegues Fernandes, João Cruz, Miguel Mira da Silva, and Rúben Pereira from Portugal cover a systematic literature review for mapping and integrating security and risk standards.

In a collaborative research between Jordan and the USA, Sahar Idwan, Junaid Zubairi, Syed Ali Haider, and Wael Etaiwi introduce their reactive traffic congestion control method based on a hierarchical graph approach.

Shahzad Riahi, Ramtin Khosravi, and Fatemeh Ghassemi from Iran conduct a study on knowledge-related policy analysis in an inference-enabled actor model.

Josival Silva, Nelson Rosa, and Fernando Aires from Brazil research and present UP-Home, a self-adaptive solution that manages the security of smart homes by industry standards, and identifies and mitigates smart home security vulnerabilities.

Last but not least, Sait Can Yucebas, Sukran Yalpir, Levent Genc, and Melike Dogan from Turkey discuss their research on price prediction and determination of the factors influencing real estate prices using X-Means clustering and CART decision trees.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Christian Gütl', with a stylized flourish at the end.

Christian Gütl, Managing Editor
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